

The Power of Co-creation

TOOLSHEET

Purpose

Short explanation to articulate the value and philosophy behind co-creation as a method for inclusive, participatory innovation and problem-solving.

Benefits

- Justification why co-creation is a valid and effective method.
- Help in designing inclusive processes that value all actors' contributions.
- Show how diverse perspectives lead to more robust, context-sensitive solutions.
- Frame your project as participatory, inclusive, and future-oriented.

Practical recommendations

Shift from thinking of stakeholders as “targets” or “beneficiaries” to co-designers of the solution. In your proposal, describe how stakeholders will be actively involved in shaping the project from the start.

Recognize that everyone brings valuable knowledge, especially from lived experience. In your proposal, explain how you will listen to and integrate different types of expertise (e.g. local knowledge, technical skills, policy insight).

Build processes that are open, iterative, and inclusive. Describe how you will facilitate workshops, co-design sessions, or feedback loops for example.

Acknowledge that solutions will evolve through collaboration. Include space in your timeline and budget for exploration, reflection, and adaptation. Frame your project as a learning journey, not just a delivery plan.

Applicability box

Main MA Skills supported

Being comfortable with co-ownership and responsibility of tasks, results, and outcomes

Active participation of, and focus on end-users

Relevant Target groups

Useful link(s)*

[Link to the explanation](#)

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